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Abstract

This deliverable highlights the critical role of software quality in enhancing scientific research reliability within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) framework. By analysing current practices and creating the Research Software Quality Kit (RSQkit), it provides actionable guidelines to improve software robustness, reproducibility, and FAIR compliance across research domains.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Introduction	6
2 Methods	7
2.1 Previous work	7
2.2 Research Software Quality practices landscaping.....	7
2.3 Survey implementation.....	8
2.4 RSQkit implementation	8
2.4.1 Content structure.....	9
2.4.2 Content processes	9
2.5 Technical aspects of software quality.....	9
3 Results and discussion	11
3.1 Research Software Quality practices landscaping.....	11
3.2 Survey	11
3.3 RSQkit	13
3.3.1 Research Software section.....	13
3.3.2 Research Software Quality Section	14
3.3.3 Your role section	14
3.3.4 Your tasks section	15
3.3.5 Research communities	15
4 Conclusions.....	17
5 Next steps.....	18
6 References.....	19

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Importance of software level (Analysis Code – Prototype Tools – Research Software Infrastructure)	6
Figure 2. Application of quality practices in the software levels from Figure 1.	7
Figure 3. Relevance of incentives to employ software quality practices	7
Figure 4. Relevance of security and performance aspects in software quality	7
Figure 5. Research Software section in the RSQkit	8
Figure 6. Research Software Quality section in the RSQkit	8
Figure 7. Your role section in the RSQkit	9
Figure 8. Your tasks section in the RSQkit	9
Figure 9. Your science domain section in the RSQkit	9

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable examines the evolving significance of software quality in scientific research, particularly within the framework of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and its science clusters. As computational demands increase, ensuring robust, maintainable, and transparent software is critical for producing credible and reproducible research outcomes. The report synthesises existing guidelines and practices, providing a roadmap to help researchers enhance software quality, reliability, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) standards across research domains.

The methodology included a comprehensive landscaping and survey of current practices among EVERSE project partners, supplemented by an interactive workshop. The survey, conducted via EUSurvey, captured perspectives from diverse fields—including humanities, bioinformatics, computer science, astronomy, and high-energy physics—with contributions from software practitioners, managers, and experts. Key insights revealed that while some quality practices are commonly implemented for research software infrastructures, their application declines for prototype tools and analysis code. Findings indicate that both internal motivations, such as improving software accuracy, and external factors, like funding, are strong incentives for quality practices.

A cornerstone of this initiative is the development of the Research Software Quality Kit (RSQkit), a toolkit designed to provide researchers with guidelines, tools, and training resources. Modelled after the Research Data Management (RDM) kit, a reference resource in research data lifecycle, the RSQkit leverages GitHub infrastructure for transparent, community-driven content creation and version control. The toolkit will include general and domain-specific practices, and will provide role-based guidance for researchers. The establishment of an editorial board further supports quality assurance and consistency in this open, collaborative resource.

Future steps involve cross-linking survey insights with RSQkit content to ensure alignment with identified community needs, expanding survey outreach beyond EVERSE partners, and refining dimensions of software quality.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the role of software in scientific research has expanded significantly [1][2], driving advancements in fields such as data analysis, modelling, and simulation. As the complexity and scale of computational tasks grow, ensuring the quality of scientific software has become paramount to the reliability and reproducibility of research outcomes.

This report aims to provide an overview of the available resources, guidelines, and best practices adopted by the wider scientific community, particularly those corresponding to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) science clusters. By reviewing established methodologies, we offer insights into how researchers within these clusters can improve software robustness, maintainability, and transparency, ultimately fostering more credible and impactful scientific results.

2 Methods

To meet one of the key objectives of WP2—providing a comprehensive overview of best practices in software quality within the research communities contributing to the EVERSE project—a comprehensive landscaping was undertaken. This was achieved through preparing and conducting a survey involving project partners, aimed at exploring and documenting the established practices.

Insights from the survey also helped in identifying the needs of various stakeholders, which are directly addressed by the RSQkit categories. The RSQkit aims to offer a carefully curated collection of guidelines, tools, and training resources, tailored to meet the diverse needs of research communities. More than just a toolkit, the RSQkit will serve as an actionable guide, offering practical advice on ensuring software is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) [3] and providing support for common tasks at different stages of the software lifecycle.

2.1 Previous work

Research Software, particularly in the context of Software Quality, has been a focal point for some time. As the first step in WP2, we aimed to present prior work done by WP members, specifically in two areas: 1) The Research Software Lifecycle from the EOSC Task Force on "Infrastructure for Quality Research Software" and 2) Software Quality Attributes from the EOSC Task Force on "Ensuring Software Quality".

- The Research Software Lifecycle document [4] outlines a variety of user stories encountered in research software development, ranging from individual researchers creating software for personal use to larger scientific communities developing well-established services. The document then explores different development approaches, shaped by the orientations of developers or maintainers. Finally, it presents a detailed research software lifecycle, offering recommendations to facilitate and implement each step, while explicitly connecting this lifecycle to the EOSC.
- The Ensure Software Quality document [5] focuses on synthesizing existing knowledge which spreads along the vast literature available, related to software quality attributes and FAIR. It provides a structured overview of key attributes and metrics, offering distinct considerations for developers, users, and service providers. With a broad array of quality attributes available, the document makes tailored recommendations for different types of Research Software.

2.2 Research Software Quality practices landscaping

In order to identify the specific aspects of practices that should be included in the survey, a 2-hour workshop was held on 31/05/2024, to discuss the *Dimensions of Software Quality Practices*. All this work was done using a MIRO board, which has been added to Zenodo [6].

Prior to the workshop, a preparatory meeting was held to set the groundwork. During this meeting, we defined the core aspects of software quality that we wanted to address. The following research questions were proposed:

- Who are the relevant stakeholders?
- What are useful sources for best practices?
- What dimensions/types of best practices should be considered?
- How to get information from the scientific communities?
- What are the best ways to collect this information?

Building on this preparation and the documents previously reviewed (see section 2.1), we organized the workshop. The initial stage of the workshop involved an exploration of the

classification of software and quality practices into different types, helping us determine which aspects should be prioritized when engaging the broader community about Research Software Quality best practices. The workshop also led to the identification of key stakeholder groups, which were later integrated into the RSQkit organisational structure, better aligning it to the unique needs of each group. For this initial stage, the topics included were:

- Software Application level and Software Lifecycle stages
- Implementation of Practice and Type of Practice
- FAIRness and Openness
- Additional software dimensions

This was followed by a discussion of the relevant aspects of quality practice types, including technical implementation, policy and management, security and ethics, and incentivisation. The aim was to identify and include all relevant aspects as widely as possible, with the workshop participants contributing to this process.

2.3 Survey implementation

A survey was set up using the EUSurvey platform. All the information related to the survey can be found in Zenodo [6]. The survey comprised questions designed to evaluate current software quality practices in the research field from the perspective of the participants, as well as requests for links and examples of quality practices where available.

The survey was designed to be filled by two distinct groups: firstly, EVERSE participants who were asked to contribute their expertise and insights as representatives of their respective research fields—including humanities, bioinformatics, computer science, astronomy, and high-energy physics—, and secondly any software expert willing to share information about their own quality practices.

The survey was designed to include flexible questions that appear only if triggered by specific selections made earlier in the survey. This adaptive structure allows questions to be tailored based on the participant's chosen perspective, and enables a refined focus on particular software types. Also, the survey limits responses to those software types that align with the participant's level of use and experience, ensuring that questions remain relevant to each respondent's expertise. The survey also helped shaping the initial contributions to the RSQkit, addressing the most urgent software quality needs expressed by the research communities already in the initial release.

Respondents participating in WP2 and the cluster pilots in WP4 were requested to complete the survey and received personal invitations to do so. All EVERSE participants were invited to contribute to the survey by accessing a general link.

2.4 RSQkit implementation

In parallel with the survey work, we have also initiated the development of the RSQkit. The content and structure of the RSQkit will be shaped by the survey results, helping to identify which practices should be included. Furthermore, the stakeholder categories identified in the initial workshop guided the organisational structure of the RSQkit, allowing it to be intuitively navigated by each type of user.

Our choice of technical infrastructure was influenced by the need for sustainability, rapid community building, and attracting external collaborators. For this reason, the RSQkit builds upon the established foundation of the RDMkit (Research Data Management toolkit) [7], which is widely used and trusted within the Life Sciences community.

Both the RDMkit and RSQkit leverage GitHub alongside GitHub Pages (<https://pages.github.com/>). Content is authored in Markdown and converted to HTML through Jekyll, enabling contributors to focus on the material while ensuring consistent site design.

GitHub's version control, issue tracking, and discussion threads further facilitate collaborative, transparent, and traceable contributions, as well as new requests for content.

2.4.1 Content structure

The RSQkit features a collection of practice guidelines, organized into web pages accessible through a structured navigation system. This navigation framework is built around the following dimensions:

- **Research Software:** Covers general aspects of research software, including the software lifecycle and the three-tier model.
- **Research Software Quality:** Focuses on key factors in research software quality, such as source code quality, FAIR principles for software, software sustainability, and open-source software.
- **Your Role:** Tailored content for different roles in research, highlighting the relevant aspects of research software for each role.
- **Your Task:** Offers specific practices related to tasks involving research software, with considerations and solutions to common challenges.
- **Research Communities:** Provides domain-specific resources related to Research Software for each scientific area involved in EVERSE.

2.4.2 Content processes

To ensure the RSQkit remains dynamic and up-to-date, contributions must be as open as possible, allowing for broad participation and sustained content development. However, maintaining quality control and consistency across the site is essential. To balance openness with oversight, we have implemented an open authoring and review process (<https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit/blob/main/CONTRIBUTING.md>).

In September 2024, an initial Editorial Board, including representatives from WP2, was established. The board is responsible for designing the contribution and editorial workflows, reviewing and approving content, managing contribution requests, and ensuring proper recognition for contributors. We plan to expand the Editorial Board in the near future and further refine the editorial processes, which are still in their early stages.

2.5 Technical aspects of software quality

Research software quality has been a subject of study by scientists, developers and engineers, with each community bringing different perspectives and developing various quality dimensions, best practices and recommendations. For example, best practices driven by developers like Open SSF [8] include a specific section for RS quality involving automation, testing and project description and documentation. From an engineering perspective, ISO Software quality models have been proposed [9] describing dozens of software quality dimensions ranging from ease of use to security or technical performance. Key industry stakeholders like Microsoft have proposed software quality attributes affecting key aspects of their tools [10]. Recently, a need for transparency, long term preservation (e.g., RS management plans [11]) and FAIR adoption (i.e., FAIR4RS [12]) has highlighted the importance of high-quality metadata when describing RS records. In this section we briefly overview the main software quality characteristics defined in the state of the art, grouping them in six main categories adopted in EVERSE.

In Task Force 2 (Technical Aspects of Software Quality), we are actively working on defining the key quality characteristics essential for EVERSE. This is an evolving effort that will continue to develop over the course of the project. Based on the quality dimensions defined in the state of the art [10][13] [14], we group existing dimensions in the following RS quality categories:

1. **Usability:** includes all the quality dimensions affecting using a software component. These include “Accessibility”, “Attractiveness”, “Ease of use”, “Installability”, “Operability”, “Recoverability”, “Reusability”.
2. **Functionality:** category that groups quality characteristics involving the main purpose of a software component. It includes quality characteristics like “Functional suitability”, “Reliability”
3. **Technical performance:** quality category that groups all characteristics affecting technical aspects of a software component. These include “Availability”, “Compatibility”, “Fault tolerance”, “Interoperability”, “Maintainability”, “Modifiability”, “Performance”, “Adaptability”, “Resource utilisation”, “Scalability”, “Time Behavior”
4. **Documentation/Technical support:** “Supportability”
5. **Testing:** “Testability”
6. **Security/Safety:** groups all aspects of quality regarding vulnerabilities and data management. It includes characteristics such as “Security”, “Safety” and “Confidentiality”

It is important to note that many quality characteristics are qualitative (e.g., Attractiveness, Ease of use, etc.) while others may have indicators that can be computed from a code repository (e.g., number of documented functions in a program, etc.). In addition, some characteristics may have a degree of overlap (e.g., tests may help documenting how a function works, documentation may help supportability and maintainability, etc.)

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Research Software Quality practices landscaping

The workshop for landscaping had 25 participants, primarily but not exclusively WP2 members. The MIRO board [6] was filled with many ideas and practices, all related to the software application level, software lifecycle, implementation of practices, type of practices, FAIRness and openness, and additional dimensions such as technical quality and incentivisation. The outcomes of the board were used to later create a survey to be shared among the Science clusters and project members.

3.2 Survey

In the following section, a summary of the survey is given. The full anonymised replies, including full text answers, can be found in Zenodo [6].

The survey was filled by 28 people, whose self-described perspective was 71.4% a personal one, 14.3% representing the research field and 14.3% a general one. This reflects discussions in the workshop where most participants expressed not feeling comfortable with answering or speaking for their field or even wider communities. The fields of research covered were, however, very broad: from Library and Information Sciences through Bioinformatics to Astronomy, as well as Computer Science in general.

Most participants were software practitioners, followed by Research Software managers and group representatives. Attendees represented all EOSC clusters, as well as additional groups from related domains.

The three-tiered model for software application classes was mostly accepted, and it was found that research software infrastructures and analysis code had the highest relative importance (in that order), see Figure 1.

Figure 1 Importance of software level (Analysis Code – Prototype Tools – Research Software Infrastructure)

While quality practices were often or always used for Research Software infrastructure, this becomes less and less frequent for prototype tools and analysis code, see Figure 2.

Figure 2 Application of quality practices in the software levels from **Figure 1**.

When asked for the incentives to apply software quality practices, the highest impacts were from receiving funding, increasing the FAIRness and the impact of software. There are both internal and external motivations actionable to improve the quality in software projects, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Relevance of incentives to employ Research Software quality practices

Figure 4 describes the relevance of security aspects in RS quality. Both for security and performance aspects, the accuracy of the output produced by the RS tool was considered the most important aspect.

Figure 4. Relevance of security and performance aspects in software quality

For ethics aspects, openness, provenance and transparency were rated highest by the respondents of the survey.

For the implementation as well as for the importance of quality aspects in the development, applying a license was the most relevant point. In the use of programming tools, the use of version control was seen as the most important and also most widely used aspect, followed by continuous integration. The survey revealed an interesting trend: while documentation was considered important, it was often not prioritized in practice. Instead, teams showed a stronger preference for documenting their work through scientific publications.

3.3 RSQkit

The RSQkit technical infrastructure has been established based on the RDMkit and the initial editorial processes put in place.

- The RSQkit link available at <https://everse.software/RSQKit/>
- The code repository for the RSQkit is <https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit>

With the EOSC Symposium (21-23 October 2024) date in mind, our goal was to have a preliminary version of the RSQkit ready for presentation. To achieve this, we compiled an initial set of pages in a spreadsheet, featuring practices relevant to the research community. Several EVERSE members contributed to this effort, resulting in the inclusion of 14 pages by the time of the symposium.

3.3.1 Research Software section

This section (Figure 5) includes a page covering general aspects of Research Software, along with two more specific pages: one on the software lifecycle and another on the three-tier view.

Research Software

Life cycle
Three-tier view
Research Software Quality
Your role
Your tasks
Your science domain
All tools and resources
All training resources

Research Software

What is Research Software?

There have been various definitions of research software - the following two definitions offer two ends of a spectrum of what research software is. The RSQKit does not mandate the definition of what research software is, however its authors and editorial board may be opinionated on what they believe the definition is and this may vary over time and be reflected in the RSQKit pages.

The following is taken from *Defining Research Software: a controversial discussion*¹ - the most recent and expansive discussion on what research software is that was done under the auspices of the [FAIR4RS RDA working group](#). We are quoting the text here from page 6:

Inclusive definition of Research Software

- All code and software artifacts that are used, produced, or might be related to the research process in one or more stages of the research lifecycle and regardless of the layer of the software stack.
- Software that was not necessarily developed with the intention of being part of research, for example, a library for interfacing with a sensor, or software that ceased to be exclusive to the research domain, for example, certain programming languages developed in research projects, e.g., Python, Scala, R.

Exclusive definition of Research Software

- Well identified software that is part of the research discovery process, which might require specialized domain knowledge and is by itself a contribution to science and research.
- Software that was developed with the intention of being part of research.

For some, the inclusive definition would be more correctly termed 'software in research' whereas the exclusive definition would be termed research software. Since the focus of the RSQKit is to highlight quality practice, most of the advice (especially around tasks) could be applied to software in research. However, many of the best practices are found in research software and we hope the RSQKit helps promote the practices to other areas of research and allows cross-pollination of ideas and practice.

On this page

- What is Research Software?
- Further topics on research software
- References

Figure 5. Research Software section in the RSQKit

3.3.2 Research Software Quality Section

This section (Figure 6) includes a general introduction to Research Software Quality and 4 more specific pages about: source code, FAIR Research Software, software sustainability and open-source software. Some of the pages included in this section are still work in progress and will be updated soon.

eosc | EVERSE | RSQKit: Research Software Quality Kit

About | Contribute | Twitter | GitHub | Search RSQKit: Research ?

Research Software
Research Software Quality
Source code
FAIR Research Software
Software Sustainability
Open Source Software
Your role
Your tasks
Your science domain
All tools and resources
All training resources

Research Software Quality

This section is focused on the definition and assessment of research software quality, keeping in mind that quality standards vary depending on the software's purpose. Metrics such as community involvement, code updates, and testing practices are useful indicators, but they only provide indirect insights into software quality, which is often subjective and context-dependent. Moreover, it should be further clarified that we recognise the challenge of balancing the software's "fit for purpose" with broader goals like reusability and long-term sustainability, noting also the non-linear relationship between quality, impact, and the potential for unintended uses.

Beyond strict technical aspects of research software quality, this page will also address additional factors that influence research software excellence, such as assessing the software's FAIRness, the Open Source nature of projects and their sustainability.

Figure 6. Research Software Quality section in the RSQKit

3.3.3 Your role section

This section (Figure 7) will cover various roles involved in working with Research Software, outlining the key considerations specific to each role. Currently, this section is still under development and will be expanded in the future.

Figure 7. Your role section in the RSQkit

3.3.4 Your tasks section

This section (Figure 8) consists of seven pages, each dedicated to a specific task commonly encountered when working with research software. These pages provide detailed descriptions of the most frequent functional areas and challenges, offering practical solutions by explaining how to use existing tools and resources.

Figure 8. Your tasks section in the RSQkit

3.3.5 Research communities

This sections right now contains three pages that are related to the EOSC Science Clusters and how they deal with research software. Specifically, ESCAPE (Figure 9), PANOSC and SSHOC have their corresponding pages in this section.

eosc EVERSE RSQKit: Research Software Quality Kit

[About](#)
[Contribute](#)
[Twitter](#)
[GitHub](#)

Research Software ▾

Research Software Quality ▾

Your role ▾

Your tasks ▾

Your science domain ▾

Physics & astronomy ▾

ESCAPE

PANOSC

Biomedical sciences

Social sciences & humanities ▾

All tools and resources

All training resources

ESCAPE ✎ ! ↻

The [ESCAPE](#) science cluster brings together communities and research infrastructures in the areas of astronomy and accelerator-based particle physics, specifically ESFRI facilities (SKAO, CTAO, KM3Net, EST, ELT, HL-LHC, FAIR) and pan-European research infrastructures (CERN, ESO, JIVE).

In ESCAPE, software applications for gathering and simulating scientific data, reaching up to exabytes, span code bases of millions of lines that are written by researchers and engineers in both compiled (e.g. C++, Cuda) and interpreted (e.g. Python) languages. With experiments existing for multiple decades, high quality, efficient and maintainable software is essential for the success of these scientific endeavours.

Main goals

- Improve access to data and tools to unlock innovation for society at large.
- Provide data with FAIR principles to increase researchers' efficiency thanks to scientific data interoperability and establish new methodological approaches and rules for quality certified data and science tools sharing.
- Build a European cross-border and multi-disciplinary open innovation environment for research data, knowledge and services, while connecting EOSC and ESFRI.
- Facilitate interdisciplinary and networked research between different sciences, through research infrastructure ecosystem and by supporting data publishing, analytics, computational capacity, virtual analysis environments and workflow systems.
- Create economies of scale, through the adoption of common approaches for data management.
- Educate and train scientific and wider user communities, to ensure the uptake of ESCAPE's results.

Services

Software catalogue

The [Open-source Scientific Software and Service Repository](#) enables researchers to save time and resources by improving the reproducibility of scientific results through high-quality software from within the community.

Other services

More services for citizen science, open data and data analysis can be found in the [ESCAPE services catalogue](#)

On this page

[Main goals](#)

[Services](#)

Figure 9. Your science domain section in the RSQkit

4 Conclusions

This deliverable has underscored the essential role of software quality in advancing scientific research. Through a comprehensive landscaping approach and survey conducted, we identified how existing practices are applied, gathered insights from the scientific community, and addressed core aspects of research software quality, including the importance of FAIR principles. The findings reveal that while quality practices are prioritized for Research Software infrastructures, their application declines for prototype tools and analysis code. From a scientist perspective, this may highlight the need for broader adoption of consistent quality measures. Alternatively, quality measures may need to be tailored to better address the unique requirements of research software depending on their tier.

The survey results also indicate that both internal motivations, like improving accuracy, and external drivers, such as funding opportunities, play a significant role in encouraging the implementation of software quality practices.

In addition, the RSQkit provides a structured, sustainable resource designed to support researchers at every stage of their projects, from initial development through to dissemination. With this toolkit, EVERSE provides a comprehensive, collaborative solution tailored to the EOSC science clusters, integrating domain-specific practices and fostering enhanced software quality and reproducibility in scientific research.

As the RSQkit evolves, it will continue to integrate contributions from diverse scientific roles and tasks, promoting sustained engagement and refinement of software quality practices. The early establishment of an editorial board will ensure the content remains both open to contributions and rigorously maintained. These initiatives together serve the wider goal of improving software quality across disciplines, thereby enhancing the credibility and impact of research outputs in the scientific community.

5 Next steps

Firstly, we will cross-link survey outputs with the RSQkit structure and content. This step involves aligning the survey insights with existing RSQkit pages to ensure that the practical needs, quality practices, and FAIR principles identified in the survey are reflected accurately and accessibly. Relevant practices and insights gathered from the survey should be incorporated into the RSQkit, ensuring an enriched resource that directly addresses the community's needs.

Next, we plan to open the survey to partners outside EVERSE. By expanding participation, we will capture additional practices, challenges, and solutions that may not have been previously considered, contributing to a more robust understanding of software quality practices across diverse research domains.

Finally, defining and validating the software dimensions will be a priority in upcoming iterations. This will involve refining and possibly expanding the dimensions established in the initial survey and workshops, such as technical implementation, policy, management, security, ethics, and incentivisation. Future iterations of the survey and RSQkit development will test these dimensions against real-world applications, ensuring they remain relevant and valuable to the scientific community.

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